

01-*Rhizophora* sp.
(mangueiro)

02-*Spondias*
mombin
(taperebá)

03-*Astrocaryum*
aculeatum
(tucumã-do-
amazonas)

04-*Astrocaryum*
vulgare
(tucumã)

05-*Mauritia*
flexuosa
(buriti)

06-*Pterocarpus*
officinalis
(mututi)

07-*Virola*
surinamensis
(ucuúba)

08-*Crinum*
americanum
(crino-branco)

09-*Combretum*
indicum (jasmim-
da-índia)

10-*Dalbergia*
monetaria
(arapari)

11-*Swartzia*
acuminata
(paracutaca)

12-*Ormosia*
coutinhoi
(buiuçu)

13-*Manicaria*
saccifera (buçu,
ubuçu)

14-*Symphonia*
globulifera
(ananin, anani)

15-*Pterocarpus*
santalinoides
(mututi)

16-*Fevillea*
cordifolia
(fevilha)

17-*Omphalea*
diandra (comadre-
do-azeite)

18-*Astrocaryum*
murumuru
(murumuru)

19-*Pachira*
aquática
(mamorana)

20-Not
identified

21-*Mucuna*
urens
(olho-de-boi,
olho-de-boto)

22-*Manilkara*
huberi
(maçarandubinha,
maçaranduba)

23-*Gnetum*
leyboldii (toá,
tuá, ituá)

24-*Antrocaryon*
amazonicum
(cedro-branco,
almeixa)

25-*Inga*
bourgonii (ingá)

26-Not identified

27-Not identified

28-Not identified

29-Not identified

30-*Attalea maripa* (inajá)

31-*Caryocar villosum* (pequi)

32-*Hevea brasiliensis* (seringueira)

33-Not identified

34-*Gustavia augusta* (jeniparana)

35-*Euterpe oleracea* (açai)

36-*Terminalia catappa* (amendoeira-da-praia)

37-*Laguncularia racemosa* (mangue tinteiro)

38-*Mucuna sloanei* (olho-de-boi, olho-de-boto)

39-*Machaerium lunatum* (aturιά, cortiça)

40-*Cocos nucifera* (coco)

41-*Terminalia dichotoma* (taninbuca)

42-*Machaerium ferox* (aturιά)

43-*Aptandra tubicina* (castanha-de-cutia)

44-*Spondias dulcis* (cajarana)

45-Not identified

46-Not identified

47-*Mangifera indica* (manga)

48-Not identified

49-Not identified

50-*Pentaclethra macroloba* (pracaxi)

51-Not identified

52-*Acrocomia aculeata* (mucajá, coco-babão)

53-Not identified

54-*Oenocarpus bacaba* (bacaba)

55-*Mora paraensis* (pracaúba)

56-*Combretum laxum* (mofumbo, tototo)

57-Not identified

58-*Raphia taedigera* (jupati)

59-Not identified

60-*Copaifera martii* (copaíba)

61-*Sacoglottis amazonica* (uxirana)

62-Not identified

63-Not identified

64-*Hymenaea courbaril* (jatobá)

65-Not identified

66-*Hymenaea parvifolia* (jutáí)

67-*Pouteria* sp.

68-Not identified

69-*Clitoria fairchildiana* (sombreiro)

70-Not identified

71-Not identified

72-*Inga cinnamomea* (ingá, inga-açú)

73-*Vatairea guianensis* (fava-bolacha)

74-Not identified

75-Not identified

76-*Inga alba*
(ingá-branca)

77-Not identified

78-Not identified

79-*Carapa guianensis*
(andiroba)

80-Not identified

81-Not identified

82-Not identified

83-Not identified

84-Not identified

85-Not identified

86-*Chrysobalanus icaco* (ajuru, ajiru, guajiru)

87-*Maclobium bifolium* (arapari-rana)

88-*Bactris cuspidata* (marajazinho, marajá)

89-*Montrichardia linifera* (aninga, aningaçu)

90-*Inga heterophylla* (ingá-vermelha, ingá-pacu)

91-*Entada polystachya* (rabo-de-macaco)

92-*Anacardium occidentale* (caju)

93-Not identified

94-Not identified

95-*Caryocar microcarpum* (pequiarana-de-várzea)

96-Not identified

97-Not identified

98-Not identified

99-Not identified

100-Not identified

101-Not identified

102-Not identified

103-Not identified

104-Not identified

105-Not identified

106-*Avicennia germinans* (siriúba)

107-Not identified

108-Not identified

109-Not identified

110-Not identified